

Wood pasture restoration for biocultural diversity and nature-based lifestyle

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Agroforestry systems can promote the renewed practices of traditional methods i.e. livestock keeping, handcraft, gastronomy etc., which have been forgotten throughout Europe in the last decades. Edible wild fruits (e.g. wild pear) were traditionally an important income from wood pastures. It was used as forage, but for gastronomy too. Wood pasture restoration could improve those uses as well. With the restoration of woody pastures, more and more farmers return to traditional methods such as agroforestry. For wooded pastures, varied land use is based on a wide variety of trees. An excellent example includes the selection, caring for and planting of wild fruit trees. Eating their fruits raw or processed may be of great benefit for farmers themselves, but it is also an extra source of income when marketed. Preparation, consumption and marketing of non-pasteurised, nutritionally complete vinegar from wooded pasture derived wild fruits has gained more popularity beside fruit jams and juices in the latest years. Besides growing and processing wild fruits, the farmer can make further profit with the processing of the high quality wool of their grazing sheep livestock. Processed products can be sold on the local market or by direct ordering. Dissemination of the procedure of traditional wool and fruit processing in folk-playhouses and

campes can further increase the turnover of the rural tourism built on the farm. In relation to the efforts made to establish an autonomous, nature-based lifestyle, a cornucopia of opportunities offered by nature is explored, allowed by the specific observations made as a result of a lifestyle continuously conducted close to nature and the implementation of new ideas derived from such observations.

Learn about the restoration of abandoned wood pastures from the AGFORWARD leaflet no. 12 “[Restoration of abandoned wood pasture](#)” available [here](#)

Figure 1. Edible wild fruits (e.g. wild pear) were traditionally an important income from wood pasture. It was used as forage, but for gastronomy too. Wood pasture restoration could improve those uses as well. (Bogyiszló, Hungary)

Further information:

http://www.eurafagroforestry.eu/files/pub/20190804_factsheet_28_en_web.pdf

[Dénes Andrea, Papp N, Babai Dániel, Czúcz Bálint, Molnár Zsolt \(2012\): Wild plants used for food by Hungarian ethnic groups living in the Carpathian Basin. Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae, 81: 381-396.](#)

[Varga, Anna \(2017\) 'Innovation from the Past.' Silvopastoral Systems in Hungary in the Light of Hungarian Ethnographic Literature. ACTA ETHNOGRAPHICA HUNGARICA, 62 \(1\). pp. 135-162. ISSN](#)

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